

Late Antique Basilicas on Cyprus

sources, contexts, histories

2: Figures

Richard Maguire 2012

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1 Cyprus: a fluid zone of transition

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1 Cyprus: a fluid zone of transition

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1 Cyprus: a fluid zone of transition

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dark grey: after Germano

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2.78 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Transverse misalignment

The arrangement at the east and west ends suggests an intention to preserve both transverse corridors. The greatest discrepancy in the transverse alignment is in the middle of the building. The ‘corrections’ west and east are an almost exact mirror image. Was there a nave altar at the point of greatest transverse misalignment, comparable with Megaw’s suggestion for a nave altar in a similar position at Soloi A? The double columns in Germano’s plan of Sion could well have marked the site of a nave altar.

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3.1 Baptisteries on Cyprus

3.2 Mazōtos-*Petounta*. Font, looking southeast

3.3 Cyprus. Baptistery plans: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

3 Baptisteries: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

3.4 Baptisteries and basilicas: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

A

C

D

3.5 Baptisteries: **A** Qal'at Sim'an (after de Vogüé 1865), **B** Holy Sepulchre (after Wharton 1995), **C** Sidé (after Eyice 1957) and **D** Gerash (after Crowfoot 1941)

3.6 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius.
Hypothetical isometric view

3.7 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Baptistery. Plan

3.8
Salamis.
Agios Epiphanius.
Baptistry. Niche
corresponding to
apodyterion, looking
southeast

3.9
Salamis.
Agios Epiphanius.
Baptistry. Niche
corresponding to font,
looking southeast

3.10 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Baptistery. *Apodyterion* looking east

3.11 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Baptistery. Font, looking southeast

3.12 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Baptistery.
Font, north arm with subsidiary tanks looking north

3.13
Salamis.
Agios Epiphanius.
Baptistry. Step in
north arm of font,
looking north

3.14 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Baptistery. Probable hypocaust, looking west

3.15 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Hypothetical route through baptistery

3.16
Salamis. Agios Epiphanius.
Corridor south of the baptistery,
looking east

3.17 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Plan

3.18 Karpasia, Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Court, looking northwest

3.19
Karpasia. Ayios Philon.
Baptistery. Court,
column base, west end
of font enclosure,
looking west

3.20
Karpasia. Ayios Philon.
Baptistery. Site of
colonette to the west
side of font opening,
looking southwest

3.21 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery.
Eastern niche in south wall of court, looking south

3.22 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. West doorway, looking west

3.23
Karpasia.
Ayios Philon.
Baptistry. Court
with west-east axis,
looking east

3.24
Karpasia.
Ayios Philon.
Baptistry. Court
with west-east axis,
looking west

3.25 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. *Apodyterion*, looking east

3.26 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Font, looking south

3.27 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Apse in font recess, looking southwest

3.28 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery.
Subsidiary tank in northeast arm of font, looking east

3.29
Karpasia. Ayios Philon.
Baptistery. Site of possible
furnace, looking northwest

3.30 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. *Chrismarion*, looking southeast

3.31 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Baptistery.
North recess in east wall of *chrismarion*, looking southeast

3.32 Karpasia. Ayios Philon. Hypothetical route from baptistery to basilica

3.33 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Plan

3.34 Ayia Trias. Baptistery, looking northwest

3.35 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Routing for the west end of the closure screen and niche in south wall of court, looking southeast

3.36 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. South wall of court, looking southeast

3.37 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Position of closure screen looking northwest

3.38 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Doorway to *apodyterion* looking east

3.39 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Font and apsidal-ended recess looking southwest

3.40 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Font looking northeast

3.41
Mazōtos-Petounta.
Font, looking west

3.42
Ayia Trias. Baptistery.
Font, north arm,
looking north

3.43
Ayia Trias. Baptistery.
Font, south arm,
looking south

3.44 Ayia Trias. Hypothetical route from baptistery to basilica

3.45 Ayia Trias. Possible *katechumenaion* looking west

3.46 Kourion. Baptistery. Plan

3.47 Kourion. Baptistery. Doorway at the north end of the narthex, looking north

3.48 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. South aisle looking west

3.49 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Detail of mosaic pavement of southwest compartment

3.50 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Detail of mosaic pavement of central compartment

3.51
Kourion.
Baptistry basilica.
Western buttness
in south aisle,
looking south

3.52 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Font facade looking south

3 Baptisteries: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

3.53 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Looking south east

3.54 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Pavements (Megaw 2007)

3.55
Kourion.
Baptistry basilica.
South west corner
of bema, looking
southwest

3.56
Kourion.
Baptistry basilica.
Western edge of bema,
looking south

3.57 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. North aisle, looking north east

3.58 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. *Kantharus* in nave floor, looking south

3.59 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Square panel in nave floor, looking east

3.60 Kourion. Baptistery basilica.
Square panel in nave floor, southeast corner, looking west

3.61 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Threshold panel in western intercolumniation of the north colonnade, looking south

3.62 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Hypothetical isometric view

3.63
Kourion. Baptistery basilica.
Narthex pavement looking south

3.64 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Narthex, pavement, inscription, looking east

3.65 Kourion. Baptistery. Probable lobby to *apodyterion*, looking west

3.66 Kourion. Baptistery. Probable *apodyterion*, entrance to font and stairs accessing platform above the font, looking east

3.67 Kourion. Baptistery. Font, looking northwest

3.68 Kourion. Baptistery. Font. Plan

3.69 Kourion. Baptistery. Font, western entrance, looking southwest

3.70 Kourion. Baptistery. *Chrismarion*, looking west

3.71 Kourion. Baptistery. Free-standing apse in *chrismarion*, looking east

3.72 Kourion. Baptistery. Free-standing apse in *chrismarion*, voussoirs (Megaw 2007)

3.73 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Corridor behind the apse, looking south

3.74 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. South end of corridor behind the apse looking west

3 Baptisteries: Agios Epiphanius, Ayios Philon, Ayia Trias and Kourion

3.75 Kourion. Hypothetical routes between the baptistery and the basilica

3.76 Kourion. Atrium looking southwest

3.77 Kourion. Hypothetical route through the baptistery basilica before the western extension of the bema

3.78 Kourion. Hypothetical routes through the baptistery the basilica after the western extension of the bema

3.79 Kourion. Baptistery basilica.
In-filled intercolumniations of the narthex, looking northeast

3.80 Kourion. Episcopal basilica. North *katechumenaion*, looking east

3.81 Pezia. Baptistery. Looking east

3.82 Pezia. Baptistery basilica.
Transverse corridor fronting the bema, looking northeast

3.83
Peyia. Hypothetical route from baptistery to baptistery basilica

3.84
Kourion. Baptistery basilica.
Hypothetical route through the baptistery before the extension of the bema

3.85
Kourion. Baptistery basilica.
Cross-section of the bema before and after the extension of the bema

3.86 Jordan. Madaba map. Holy Sepulchre complex and possible baptistery

3.87 Jerusalem. Holy Sepulchre complex. Baptistery. Hypothetical plans and routes:
 A Conant, B Doval, C Khatchatrian and D Wharton

3.88 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Font, cross-section

3.89 Kourion. Baptistery basilica. Font, cross-section

3.90 Kourion. Baptistery. Font recess looking south

3.91 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery.
Opus sectile paving in west aisle, detail

3.92 Karpas. Ayios Philon.
Baptistry. *Opus sectile* paving in west aisle (du Plat Taylor and Megaw 1981)

3.93 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Detail of *opus sectile* paving inside star motif in west aisle

3.94 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Blocked apse in east aisle, looking southeast

3.95 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery, skirting in east aisle, looking east

3.96 Karpas, Ayios Philon: Baptistery. *Opus sectile* paving in east aisle looking north (inset: du Plat Taylor and Megaw 1981)

3.97 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. *Opus sectile* paving in court (du Plat Taylor and Megaw 1981)

3.98 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. *Opus sectile* paving in south east corner of court looking south

3.99 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Raised east aisle, looking south

3.100 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery.
Apsidal recess in east wall of *chrismarion*, looking east

3.101
Karpas. Ayios Philon.
Baptistry. *Opus sectile*
paving in lobby to the
east of the *apodyterion*
looking south

3.102 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistry. *Apodyterion* looking east

3.103
Karpas. Ayios Philon.
Baptistry. *Opus sectile*
paving in the *chrismarion*
(Megaw)

3.104 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistery. Detail of *opus sectile* vortex in *chrismarion*

3.105 Karpas. Ayios Philon. Baptistry. Hypothetical Phase 1 with Phase 2

3.106 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Hypothetical Phase 1 with Phase 2

3.107 Ayia Trias. Baptistery. Exterior of east apse of *chrismarion* looking west

3.108 Kourion. Baptistery. *Chrismarion* looking southwest

4 Apses: Lythrankomi, Kiti and Livadia

- 29 Kiti: Angeloktisti
- 38 Livadia: Panayia tis Kyras
- 40 Lythrankomi: Panayia Kanakariá

4.1 Apse mosaics on Cyprus

4.2 Salamis. Agios Epiphanius. Sixth century alterations (Phase 1 in grey)

4.3 Kourion. Episcopal basilica. Sixth century alterations (Phase 1 in grey)

4.4 Soloi. Sixth century alterations (Phase 1 in grey)

4.5
Paphos. Chrysopolitissa.
Sixth century alterations
(Phase 1 in grey)

4.6 Distribution of synthronona

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ② Akanthou / Tattisu:
Panayia Pergameniotissa ⑥ Amathus: Acropolis basilica ⑪ Aphendrika: Asomatos ⑫ Aphendrika: Panayia ⑬ Ayia Moni ⑮ Germasoyeia-Kalogeroi ⑲ Kalavastos: Area II ⑳ Kalavastos-Sirmata ㉑ Karpas: Ayios Philon ㉒ Kiti: Angeloktisti ㉓ Kourion: Extra-mural basilica ㉔ Kourion: Limeniotissa | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ㉖ Lambousa / Lapithos / Lapta:
Acheiropoietos ㉗ Limassol: Tychikos / Nemesios? ㉘ Livadia: Panayia tis Kyras ㉙ Paphos: Chrysopolitissa ㉚ Peyia: Central basilica ㉛ Peyia: North basilica ㉜ Peyia: South basilica ㉝ Salamis: Agios Epiphanius ㉞ Salamis: Agios Varnavas ㉟ Salamis: Campanopetra Ⓜ Soloi Ⓝ Sykha: Panayia Ⓞ Syngrasis / Sinirüstü:
Ayios Procopius |
|--|---|

4.7
Poreč.
Episcopal throne (c.550).
(Prelog 1986)

4.8
Libya. Apollonia.
Central basilica
(c.533-565).
Throne at south end of
narthex, looking south

4.9
Amathus.
Acropolis
basilica. Main
apse, looking
southeast

4.10
Peyia. Central
basilica.
Main apse
looking east

4.11
Kalavassos-
Sirmata.
Central apse
looking
northeast

4.12 Lythrankomi. Semi-dome. Main apse. Enthroned Theotokos (Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

4.13 Lythrankomi. Reconstruction of east end (Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

4.14
Kiti. Semi-dome.
Theotokos

4.15
Kiti. Late 19th century plan
(Foulias 2004)

4.16 Livadia. Apse looking east. (condition in 2009)

4.17 Milan. San Lorenzo. Chapel of Sant' Aquilino.
Apse mosaic (late fourth century) (Bertelli *et al* 1988)

4.18 Campanopetra. Main apse looking east

4.19 Campanopetra.
Kyklion looking southeast

4.20 Campanopetra. Reconstruction of
episcopal throne and recess in
kyklion (Roux 1998)

4.21 Campanopetra. Axial recess in *kyklion* looking southwest

4.22 Rome. S.Pudenziana. Reconstruction (Mathews 1995)

4.23 Rome.
S.Pudenziana.
Christ teaching

San Venanzio apse

4.24 Rome. Lateran baptistery. Chapel of S.Venanzio.
Apse mosaic (fifth century) (Matthiae 1967)

4.25 Rome. Lateran baptistery. Chapel of S.Venanzio.
Apse. S.Domnion and Pope Theodore (Ladner 1941)

4.26 Lythrankomi. Suppedaneum (Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

4.27 Kiti. Suppedaneum

4.28 Livadia. Suppedaneum (after Megaw and Hawkins 1976)

4.29 Campanopetra. Reconstruction of the east end (Roux 1998)

4.30 Peyia. Central basilica (after Papageorgiou 1986)

4.31 Amathus. Southwest basilica. East end, looking southeast

4.32 Amathus. Southwest basilica (after Papageorghiou 1986)

4.33 Kalavasos-*Sirmata*. Reconstruction after Rautman (2003)

4.34 Kalavasos-*Sirmata* (after Rautman 2003)

4.35 Kalavassos-*Sirmata*. Bema (Rautman 2003)

4.36
Kalavassos.
Area V.
altar

4.37 Episkopi. Altar from the Episcopal basilica at Kourion (Megaw 2007)

4.38 Lythrankomi. Apse mosaic (reconstruction, Megaw and Hawkins 1976)

4.39 Kiti. Apse mosaic

4.40
Rabbula Gospels, folio 13v.
Ascension. Syria 586
(Florence, Biblioteca
Medicea Laurenziana,
cod. Plut. 1.56)

4.41 *Sella curulis* (Mathews 1995)

4.42
Livadia. Theotokos
(after Megaw and Hawkins 1976)

4.43 Rome. S.M in Trastevere.
Maria Regina (705-7)
(Belting 1994)

4.44 Rome. S.M. Antiqua.
Maria Regina, palimpsest wall,
third layer. Sixth century
(thehistoryblog.com)

4.45 Rome. S.M. Maggiore.
Jerusalem. Left spandrel of
triumphal arch. (Karpp 1996)

4.46 Rome. S.M. Maggiore.
Bethlehem. Right spandrel of
triumphal arch. (Karpp 1996)

4.47 Rome. S.M.Maggiore. Christ enthroned. Left side of triumphal arch. (Karpp 1996)

4.48 Rome. S.M.Maggiore. Priests and Levites carry the Ark. Nave south wall. (Karpp 1996)

4.49 Rome. S.M.Maggiore. The Ark carried across the the Jordan. Nave south wall. (Karpp 1996)

4.50 Rome. S.M.Maggiore. The Ark carried around Jericho. Nave south wall. (Karpp 1996)

4.51 Varna reliquary.
Inner casket.

4.52 Raphael. Pope Sylvester 1 carried in the *Sedia Gestatoria* (Gardner Museum of Art Boston)

4.53 *Sedia Gestatoria* (en.wikipedia.org)

4.54
Germigny-des-Prés.
Apse mosaic, c.806
(en.wikipedia.org)

4.55 Kiti. Angel

4.56
Lythrankomi. Reconstruction
(Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

4.57 Soloi. Ciborium (des Gagniers and Tinh 1985)

4.58 Campanopetra. Ciborium (Roux 1998)

4.59 Rabbula Gospels. Folio 1v. Virgin and Child. Syria 586
(Florence, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, cod. Plut. 1.56)

4.60 Sinai. Angel. Triumphal arch. North side (Forsyth and Weitzmann 1973)

4.61 Sinai. Angel. Triumphal arch. South side (Forsyth and Weitzmann 1973)

4.62
Pigna at Old St Peter's
(Bartoli in Finch 1991)

4.63 Morphou/Güzelyurt. S.Mamas. Ciborium ceiling (1500-1550). (Bolman 2010)

4.64 Riha. Ripidion. Front (Dumbarton Oaks Collection: acc.no. 36.23)

4.65 Riha. Ripidion. Back (Dumbarton Oaks Collection: acc.no. 36.23)

4.66 Stuma. Ripidion. Front (Istanbul Archaeological Museum: acc.no. 3758)

4.67 Germigny-des-Prés. Apse mosaic. Detail

4.68
Plate, dated
Constantinople 547-550
(Ferrell Collection. Spier 2010)

4.69 Lythrankomi. Detail (Megaw and Hawkins 1977)

4.70 Fertile crescent (ancient.eu.com)

4.71a Livadia. Reconstruction (Megaw and Hawkins 1976)

4.71b
Livadia.
Condition in
1961 (ARDA)

4.72
Livadia. Apse.
Semi-dome
(condition in
2009)

4.73 Rabbula Gospels. Folio 13v. Ascension. Syria 586
(Florence, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, cod. Plut. 1.56)

4.74 Khirbet el-Maqerqesh.
Gaia (late fifth century).
(Hachlili 2009)

4.76 Jordan. Mount Nebo.
Upper Chapel of Priest John.
Gaia (second half sixth century).
(Hachlili 2009)

4.75
Antioch.
Constantinian Villa.
Autumn (first half
fourth century)
(Cimok 2000)

4.77 Jordan. Madaba. House of Hippolytus (Piccirillo 1997)

4.78-81 Jordan. Madaba. House of Hippolytus: four seasons. (Piccirillo 1997)

4.82 Jordan. Madaba. House of Hippolytus: Tychae of Rome, 'Gregoria' and Madaba. (Piccirillo 1997)

4.83 Winged personification of spring (Egypt, sixth century) (Benaki Museum, Athens)

4.84
Paphos and Cyprus.
Eastern Mediterranean
(Michaelides 2005)

4.85
Constantine and the
Tyche of Constantinople.
Fourth-century sardonyx
(Hermitage St. Petersburg)

4.86
Solidus of Theodosius II
(struck 423-4)
(historicalcoins.com)

4.87
Rome. S. Pudenziana.
Jewelled cross

4.88
Solidus of Anastasius I
(struck 498)
(cngcoins.com)

4.89
Solidus of Justin I
(struck 519-527)
(cngcoins.com)

4.90
Pentanummium of Justin I.
Tyche of Antioch wearing
a turreted crown
(struck 518-527)
(Wildwinds.com)

4.91
Solidus of Justin II.
Seated Constantinopolis
(struck 565-578)
(historicalcoins.com)

4.92
Solidus of Justin II
and Tiberius II.
Male Victory holding
a cross (578).
(cngcoins.com)

4.93 Constantinople. Blachernai and Pege

4.94 Bronze stamp. KARPOI (fruits).
(Maguire 1989)

4.95 Bronze stamp. HYGEIA (health)
(Maguire 1989)

4.96
Ravenna. S.Vitale.
Empress Theodora.
Sanctuary, south wall
(completed 547)
(no.wikipedia.org)

4.97 Egyptian lunate necklace. Early seventh century. (Antikenmuseum, Berlin)

4.98
Rabbula Gospels.
Folio 13v. Ascension (586).
Detail

4.99a
Artemis. 2nd century.
(Museo Archeologico Nazionale
di Napoli. Farnese Coll.)

4.99b
Marble statuette of Ephesian Artemis
from Salamis. 2nd century.
(Güzelyurt Museum)

4.100
Orant Virgin from the Chapel of John VII
in Old St Peter's (Chiesa di San Marco,
Florence and Biblioteca Apostolica.
Barb. Lat. 2732, fols 76v-77r)

4.102
Hematite pendant with an orant
alongside an inscription suggesting
healing associated with an issue of
blood (Metropolitan Museum, New York)

4.101
Gold bracelet (c.600),
Eastern Mediterranean,
possibly Syria (British
Museum PE AF 351)

4.103
Salamis. Mural crowned
female, possibly a Tyche
from an offering table
(Cyprus Museum, Nicosia)

4.104
Paphos. House of Aion. Triclinium,
Leda and the Swan panel.
Personification of Lacedaemonia
(second half, fourth century)
(Michaelides 1992)

4.105
Paphos. Villa of Theseus. Room 38,
south wing. Theseus and the Minotaur.
Personification of Crete (third century)
(Michaelides 1992)

4.106 Vrap cup. Tyche of Cyprus (Metropolitan Museum. New York) (Rumsey)

4.107
Tyche of Rome

4.108
Tyche of Alexandria

4.109
Tyche of Constantinople

4.110 Cyprus treasure (641-51). Plate with military saint (British Museum)

4.111 Livadia. Panagia tis Kyras, looking west

4.112
Livadia.
Panagia tis Kyras.
Plan (after Megaw
and Hawkins 1971)

4.113 Livadia. Panagia tis Kyras.
Limestone column

4.114 Livadia. Panagia tis Kyras.
Re-used Proconnesian chancel
screen post. North crossing arm,
west side.

4.115 Livadia. Panagia tis Kyras. Re-used Proconnesian chancel screen post.
North crossing arm, east side.

4.116 Ravenna. S. Apollinare in Classe. Archangels Gabriel and Michael (Bustacchi 1988)

4.117
Egypt 250-280
(John Rylands Library, Manchester)

4.118
Schutzmantelmadonna
(Berlin. Bode museum. Ravensburg c.1480)

4.119 Ghirlandaio *Madonna della Misericordia* (Vespucci Chapel, Florence. C.1472)

5.1 Peyia. Baptistery basilica. Plan

5.2 Peyia. Baptistery basilica.
North T-shaped pier and respond against north wall, looking north

5.3
Akrotiri.
Katalymmata ton Plakoton.
Plan (after Procopiou 2009)

5.4
Katalymmata ton Plakoton.
Medallion (Dept. of Antiquities)

5.5
Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Atrium.
Southwest pier

5.6
Katalymmata ton Plakoton.
Atrium and east
arm of Structure A,
looking southwest

5.7 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Bema, looking west

5.8 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Central apse, looking northwest

5.9 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Bema pavement. Deer

5.10 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Bema pavement. Bird pecking grapes

5.11 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Chancel screen panel (Dept. of Antiquities)

5.12 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
North apsidiole in west wall, looking northeast

5.13 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Reliquary lid

5.14 Varna. Marble reliquary. (Buschhausen 1971)

5.15 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. South apsidiole in west wall with fragments of probable *mensa martyris*, looking northwest

5.16 Salamis. Agios Varnavas. *Mensa martyris* in south apsidiole, looking east

5.17 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. South apsidiole, looking southwest

5.18 Salamis. Agios Varavas.
Hellenistic and Roman cemetery.
Sarcophagus lid

5.19 Salamis. Agios Varavas.
Hellenistic and Roman cemetery.
Sarcophagus lid

5.20 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
Sarcophagus, south apsidiole, looking southeast

5.21 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
South apsidiole. Embedded sarcophagus lid, looking west

5.22 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
Mosaic panel at eastern threshold to bema (Dept. of Antiquities)

5.23 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. North apsidiole, looking northwest

5.24 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
Ambulatory of south transept arm, looking north (Dept. of Antiquities)

5.25 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
South east corner of southern ambulatory, looking southeast

5.26 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A.
Champlévé panel from the southwest corner of the southern ambulatory

5.27
Katalymmata ton Plakoton.
Structure A. *Opus sectile
crustae*, more than one of
which may have come from
a figure (Dept. of Antiquities)

5.28
Peyia. Baptistery basilica.
Opus sectile crustae.
(Dept. of Antiquities)

5.29 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Mosaic paving

5.30 Katalymmata ton Plakoton. Structure A. Mosaic paving

5.31 Apendrika Panagia. South aisle looking southwest

5.32 Apendrika-Asomatos.
South aisle looking east

5.33 Sykha.
South aisle looking east

5.34
Katalymmata
ton Plakoton.
Structure A.
Doorway to the
west corridor
the south arm,
looking east.

5.35
Soloï.
Apsidal south
end of narthex,
looking south

5.36 Cyprus. Orientation of basilicas. Representative sample

- | | | |
|----------------------------|-------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| ① Akamas: Ayios Kononas | ②④ Kalavassos: Area II | ④⑧ Paphos: Panayia |
| ② Akanthou / Tatlisu: | ②⑤ Kalavassos: Area V | Limeniotissa |
| Panayia Pergamieniotissa | ②⑥ Kalavassos- <i>Sirmata</i> | ⑤⑩ Paphos: Toumballos |
| ③ Akrotiri: Katalymmata | ②⑦ Karpas: Ayios Philon | ⑤① Peyia: Baptistery basilica |
| ton Plakoton | ②⑨ Kiti: Angeloktisti | ⑤② Peyia: Central basilica |
| ⑤ Alassa: Ayia Mavri | ③① Kourion: Baptistery | ⑤③ Peyia: North basilica |
| ⑥ Amathus: | basilica | ⑤④ Peyia: South basilica |
| Acropolis basilica | ③② Kourion: Episcopal | ⑤⑤ Polis: <i>Arsinoe</i> (EG0) |
| ⑦ Amathus: Ayios Tykhonas | basilica | ⑤⑥ Polis: <i>Chrysochous</i> (EF2) |
| ⑧ Amathus: Episcopal | ③④ Kourion: Limeniotissa | ⑤⑨ Salamis: Agios Epiphanius |
| basilica | ③⑤ Kourion: Nymphaeum | ⑥⑩ Salamis: Agios Varnavas |
| ⑨ Amathus: South-west | basilica | ⑥① Salamis: Campanopetra |
| basilica | ③⑧ Livadia / Sazliköy: | ⑥② Salamis: Forum basilica |
| ⑩ Amathus: Ayia Varvara | Panayia tis Kyras | ⑥③ Salamis: Hagiasma of |
| ⑫ Aphenrika: Panayia | ④⑩ Lythrankomi / Boltasli: | Nicodemus |
| ⑬ Geroskipou: Agioi Pente | Panayia Kanakariá | ⑥④ Soloi A |
| ⑭ Gialousa-Sipahi / Yeni | ④① Marathovouno / Ulukisla | ⑥④ Soloi B |
| Erenköy: Ayia Trias | ④② Maroni- <i>Petrera</i> | ⑥⑥ Sykha: Panayia |
| ⑰ Gialousa / Yeni Erenköy: | ④⑤ Nicosia: Bedestan | ⑥⑦ Syngراسis / Sinirüstü: |
| Agios Phōtios | ④⑥ Nicosia: St. George's Hill | Ayios Procopius |
| ⑱ Golgoi | ④⑦ Paphos: Chrysopolitissa | |

5.37 Polis-Arsinoë.
Apse in north wall, looking west

5.38 Kourion.
Extra-mural basilica. Apse in north wall looking northwest

5.39 Amathus. Ayios Tykhonas.
Three apses on the north side of the basilica, looking southeast.

5.40 Thessalonika. St Demetrios (629-34) (after Krautheimer 1986)

5.41 Philippi. Basilica A (c.500) (after Koukouli-Chrysanthaki and Bakirtzis 2006)

5.42 Perge. Basilica A (fifth or sixth century) (after Rott 1908)

5.43 Perge. Basilica B (fourth century) (after Rott 1908)

5.44
Antioch-Kaoussié (387)
(after Krautheimer 1986)

5.45 Qal'at Sim'an (c.470) (after Krautheimer 1986)

5.46 Rusafa. Basilica B (490-520) (after Donceel-Voûte 1987)

5.47 Serdjilla (372?) (after Donceel-Voûte 1987)

5.48 Et-Tabgha (c.500) (after Krautheimer 1986)

5.49 Aristoboulias (early fifth century) (after Ovadiah 1970)

5.50 Marea (sixth century) (after McKenzie 2007)

5.51 Hermopolis Magna (c.430-40) (after McKenzie 2007)

5.52 Constantinople. Blachernai: hemicycle 518-527. (after Mango 1998)

5.53 Constantinople. Sergius and Bacchus (527-536) Inscription (photo JC)

5.54 Ābū Mīnā. Phase 1 (395-408) (after McKenzie 2007)

5.55 Ābū Mīnā. Phase 2 (c.475) (after McKenzie 2007)

5.56 Ābū Mīnā. Mural apse in north wall of north transept looking northwest (photo JC)

5.57 Ābū Mīnā. Mural apse in south wall of south transept looking southwest (photo JC)

5.58 Ābū Mīnā. Ambulatory looking southwest. (photo JC)

5.59 Ābū Mīnā. Passage between the inner and outer apses looking southeast (photo JC)

5.61 Rome. Lateran. Fastugium. (324) (after Brandenburg 2005)

6.1 Cyprus plates. Relative sizes (after Dodd 1961 and Wander 1973)

